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Health Risk Assessment of Heavy Metals Contamination in Soil Samples from Dandagoro Settlement, Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Heavy metals are environmental pollutants that pose potential health risks to human populations. This study assessed the concentrations and associated health risks of Co, Cr, Pb, Cd, and Cu in soils collected from Dandagoro settlement. The mean concentrations followed the order $Co > Cr > Pb > Cu > Cd$, with values of 0.225 ± 0.289 , 0.110 ± 0.218 , 0.106 ± 0.066 , 0.00110 ± 0.00084 , and 0.00224 ± 0.00097 mg/kg, respectively. These concentrations were below the WHO's permissible limits, indicating minimal contamination. Pollution indices including the Contamination Factor (CF), Pollution Load Index (PLI), and Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo}) confirmed low contamination levels, while localized Co elevation suggests minor anthropogenic influence. Non-carcinogenic risk assessments based on the Hazard Quotient (HQ) showed values below 1.0 for both children and adults, indicating no significant health threat. However, carcinogenic risk assessment revealed elevated Lifetime Cancer Risk (LCR) values for Cr in children, with a maximum of 5.31×10^{-6} , surpassing the safe threshold of 1.0×10^{-6} . These findings suggest that while the overall risk remains low, children in agricultural or waste-disposal zones of Dandagoro may face increased cancer risk from Cr exposure. Continued monitoring and public health interventions are recommended to mitigate long-term exposure.

Keywords: soil contamination, toxicity, human health, risk characterization, environmental pollution.

INTRODUCTION

Heavy metal contamination poses a significant global environmental and public health challenge due to its bioaccumulation potential, and toxicological effects (Afolayan et al., 2021). In sub-Saharan Africa, rapid urbanization, industrial expansion, and inadequate waste management have exacerbated exposure risks, with Nigeria being particularly vulnerable due to its growing industrial and agricultural sectors (Samaila et al., 2023). Among the most concerning heavy metals are cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), cobalt (Co), Arsenic (As), Zinc (Zn) and nickel (Ni), which are known for their toxicity, environmental persistence, and ability to accumulate in biological systems (Afolayan et al., 2021; Kawichai et al., 2023). These contaminants originate from both natural processes and anthropogenic activities, including industrial emissions, agricultural runoff, and improper waste disposal (Hasaballah et al., 2021). Chronic exposure of these metals, whether through ingestion, inhalation, or dermal contact, has been linked to severe health disorders, including renal dysfunction, neurological damage, and carcinogenesis (Shuvo et al., 2025).

The Dandagoro settlement in Katsina State, Nigeria, exemplifies a rapidly developing area where increasing human activities such as waste dumping, engine oil spills, and fertilizer use may contribute to heavy metal pollution (Uba et al., 2022; Samaila et al., 2023). While prior study in the region by (Samaila et al., 2023), reported heavy metal concentrations in soil below WHO thresholds, long-term bioaccumulation in the food chain remains a critical concern (Uba et al., 2022). For instance, even low-level exposure to Pb and Cd has been associated with neurotoxicity and kidney damage, while Cr and Co may contribute to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Jaishankar et al., 2014).

Recent investigations in Katsina State underscore these risks. A study of agricultural soils across the Katsina, Daura, and Funtua zones found that while Cd, Pb, Cr, and Zn levels were generally within permissible limits, children in the Daura zone exhibited an Incremental Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) for Pb exceeding safe thresholds, indicating long-term carcinogenic potential (Yaradua et al., 2022). Similarly, vegetables grown near metal workshops in Kofar Marusa showed elevated Pb, Cr, and Ni concentrations, with spinach and cabbage demonstrating the highest uptake (Kabir et al., 2024). Furthermore, *Moringa oleifera* leaves irrigated with contaminated water from River Ginzo, Katsina, posed significant carcinogenic risks due to Ni, with ILCR values surpassing U.S. EPA safety limits (Alhassan & Dajal, 2023). In Jibia Local Government Area, illegal mining activities led to Fe, Cu, and Pb levels in *Moringa* leaves exceeding maximum allowable concentrations (MAC), with combined hazard indices ($HRI > 1$) and higher ILCR values for Ni, highlighting severe food safety risks (Yaradua et al., 2023).

This study will investigate the concentration of heavy metals in soil sediments from Dandagoro settlement and assess the potential health threats associated with these contaminants. The primary objectives are to determine the pollution levels of heavy metals of Cr, Cu, Cd, Pb, and Co in soil samples, evaluate the non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic risks using standardized exposure assessment parameters, and compare the results with international standards and guidelines. The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the environmental and health impacts of heavy metal contamination in the region and will inform future policy decisions for environmental protection and public health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was carried out in Dandagoro, a rural settlement situated in the Batagarawa Local Government Area of Katsina State, Nigeria's North-western geopolitical zone. Katsina State borders the Republic of Niger to its north and is surrounded by Kaduna, Kano, and Zamfara States to its south, east, and west, respectively. The state records an average annual rainfall of about 1,312 mm, a mean temperature of 27.3°C, and an average relative humidity of 50.2% (Kabir et al., 2024; Samaila et al., 2025). Dandagoro itself is located at coordinates 13.0806° N and 7.6764° E, approximately 7 km northeast of Katsina city, the state capital. This area lies within the Sudan savannah ecological zone, characterized by a tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons, relatively dry conditions, sparse vegetation, and seasonal rainfall (Samaila et al., 2023). The local economy is primarily sustained by agriculture, mainly subsistence farming and animal rearing.

Figure 1 presents a map of the study area, illustrating the sampling locations. Samples were collected in May 2023 from a 100-meter-long transect, divided into ten equal grids (B1-B10). One sample per grid was collected at 10-meter intervals (0-10, 10-20, ..., 90-100 meters). Geographic coordinates and altitude were recorded using a Garmin GPSMAP 65 handheld GPS device (Table S1). Samples were then analysed in the laboratory.

Figure 1: Map showing the location of the study area: (A) Batagarawa LGA (Paintmaps, 2025) (B) Dandagoro settlement (Google earth, 2025)

Sample Preparation and Analysis

Soil samples were initially sieved and air-dried at ambient laboratory temperature. Subsequently, they were manually crushed using a mortar and pestle to achieve a fine consistency suitable for chemical analysis. A spatula and analytical balance were used to accurately weigh 0.5 g of each sample, which was then transferred to a Teflon beaker. The beakers were placed in a fume hood for safety during the digestion process. The samples were digested using a mixture of concentrated nitric acid (HNO₃) and concentrated perchloric acid (HClO₄) in a 2:1 volumetric ratio. Following digestion, the samples were transferred to an oven and heated at 200°C to facilitate complete decomposition. Once cooled, the residues were diluted with 5 mL of 20% nitric acid solution. The resulting solutions were then filtered, and deionized water was added to adjust the final volume to 100 mL.

Prior to analysis, a blank determination was performed using the atomic absorption spectrometer (Unicam Solar A.A.S 969 model) without introducing a sample to establish baseline readings. The prepared samples were subsequently dissolved and aspirated into the spectrometer for metal analysis. Another blank determination was conducted under identical conditions to ensure accuracy and eliminate potential interferences. The absorbance values and corresponding concentrations of each element were measured and plotted to construct a calibration graph. The calibration curve was used to quantify the metal concentrations in the samples, following the methodology outlined by (Bello et al., 2016).

Assessment of Heavy Metals Pollution

Contamination Factor and Degree of contamination

Contamination Factor (CF) measures the pollution level of a single pollutant in soil or sediment samples while Degree of contamination (DC) quantifies total pollution in soil or sediment by summing the contamination factors of all measured pollutants at a site.

$$CF = \frac{C_i}{C_{background}} \quad (1)$$

Where C_i is the concentration of the metal and $C_{background}$ is the reference background concentration. Classification of CF: Low ($CF < 1$), Moderate ($1 \leq CF < 3$), Considerable ($3 \leq CF < 6$), Very high ($CF \geq 6$) (Hasaballah et al., 2021; Bello et al., 2016).

Pollution Load Index

Pollution Load Index (PLI) measures the overall level of pollution in a sampling area. It is expressed in equation (2).

$$PLI = (CF_1 \times CF_2 \dots\dots\dots CF_n)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (2)$$

Where CF_n represents contamination factors for n pollutants. Classification of PLI: $PLI < 1$ (No pollution), $PLI \geq 1$ (Pollution) (Adamu et al., 2023; Bello et al., 2016).

Geo-Accumulation Index

The Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo}) measures the degree of contamination in soils or sediments by comparing the concentration of a pollutant to its natural background level, accounting for both natural and anthropogenic contributions. It can be calculated from equation (4).

$$I_{geo} = \text{Log}_2 \left[\frac{C_n}{1.5 \times B_n} \right] \quad (3)$$

where C_n is the measured concentration of metal n , and B_n is the background geochemical value. The value 1.5 corrects for lithogenic fluctuations. Classification of I_{geo} : unpolluted ($I_{geo} \leq 0$), from unpolluted to moderately polluted ($0 < I_{geo} \leq 1$), moderately polluted ($1 < I_{geo} \leq 2$), from moderately to strongly polluted ($2 < I_{geo} \leq 3$), strongly polluted ($3 < I_{geo} \leq 4$), from strongly to extremely polluted ($4 < I_{geo} \leq 5$), and extremely polluted ($I_{geo} > 5$) (Adamu et al., 2023; Kawichai et al., 2023).

Assessment of Health Risk from Heavy Metals

Non Cancer Effect Evaluation

Humans may be exposed to heavy metals in polluted soils through three primary pathways: ingestion, inhalation, and dermal routes. The potential health risks associated with these exposure routes are estimated using the average daily intake (ADI) of heavy elements for each pathway.

The equations for estimating ADI through each exposure route are as follows:

$$ADI_{ing} = \frac{(C \times IR_{ing} \times EF \times ED)}{(BW \times AT)} \times 10^{-6} \quad (4)$$

$$ADI_{inh} = \frac{(C \times IR_{inh} \times EF \times ED)}{(PEF \times BW \times AT)} \quad (5)$$

$$ADI_{dermal} = \frac{(C \times SA \times DAF \times EF \times ED \times SAF)}{(BW \times AT)} \times 10^{-6} \quad (6)$$

$$ADI = ADI_{ing} + ADI_{inh} + ADI_{dermal} \quad (7)$$

C is the Concentration of the metal in soil (mg/kg, measured in this work), IR_{ing} is the Ingestion rate (mg/day), IR_{inh} is the Inhalation rate (m^3/day), EF is the Exposure frequency (days/year), ED is the Exposure duration (years), SA is the Exposed skin area (cm^2), SAF is the Soil adherence factor (mg/cm^2), DAF is the Dermal absorption factor (dimensionless), PEF is the Particulate emission factor (m^3/kg), BW is the Body weight (kg), AT is the Average exposure time (days) and ADI is the cumulative average daily metal intake (Olagunju et al., 2020; Aguilera et al., 2021). The constant values used for each parameter in this research are provided in Table S2.

Non - Carcinogenic Risk Assessment

The hazard quotient (HQ) is a dimensionless quantity used in human health risk assessments to estimate the non-carcinogenic risk posed by exposure to individual metals or other contaminants. For metals, the HQ is calculated as

$$HQ = \frac{ADI_{metal}}{RFD_{metal}} \quad (9)$$

where ADI_{metal} is the average daily dose ($mgkg^{-1}day^{-1}$) absorbed via exposure routes (e.g., ingestion, inhalation, dermal contact), and RfD_{metal} is the metal-specific reference dose derived from toxicological studies. The RfD_{metal} specific values can be found in Table S3. Hazard Index (HI) is the summation of the HQ values of all contaminants detected from the soil sample. HI was used to calculate the cumulative non carcinogenic effects as a result of contamination by multiple metals.

$$HI = HQ_1 + HQ_2 \dots + HQ_n \quad (10)$$

HI value ≤ 1 indicates that exposure is within the acceptable range, while values > 1 suggest potential health risks (Olagunju et al., 2020; Yaradua et al., 2022).

Carcinogenic Risk Assessment

Carcinogenic risk assessment evaluates the probability of cancer development due to long-term exposure to metals classified as carcinogens. The lifetime cancer risk (LCR) is quantified using the following equations for each exposure pathway:

$$LCR_{ing} = ADI \times CSF_{ing} \quad (11)$$

$$LCR_{inh} = ADI \times CSF_{inh} \quad (12)$$

$$LCR_{dermal} = ADI \times CSF_{dermal} \quad (13)$$

where LCR_{ing} , LCR_{inh} , and LCR_{dermal} denote the lifetime cancer risks via ingestion, inhalation, and dermal contact, respectively. ADI is the average daily intake, and CSF_{ing} , CSF_{inh} , and CSF_{dermal} are the cancer slope factors for carcinogenic metals (Pavilonis et al., 2017). Their specific values are enumerated in Table S3.

The total carcinogenic risk (LCR) is the sum of pathway specific LCR values.

$$LCR = LCR_{ing} + LCR_{inh} + LCR_{dermal} \quad (14)$$

The acceptable threshold for cancer risk is 1.0×10^{-4} , while the regulatory tolerable values for lifetime cancer risk (LCR) ranges between 1.0×10^{-6} and 1.0×10^{-4} (Hasaballah et al., 2021; Pavilonis et al., 2017).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Heavy Metal Concentrations

Table S4 highlights the levels of heavy metal concentrations in the soil samples of Dandagoro settlement. The concentrations of cobalt, chromium, lead, cadmium, and copper in the soil samples ranges from 0.0024 to 1.01 mg/kg, 0.0033 to 0.725 mg/kg, 0.0125 to 0.211 mg/kg, 0.0003 to 0.0034 mg/kg, and 0.0001 to 0.0024 mg/kg, respectively. The mean concentrations (Mean \pm S.D.) of these metals were 0.225 ± 0.289 mg/kg for Co, 0.110 ± 0.218 mg/kg for Cr, 0.106 ± 0.066 mg/kg for Pb, 0.00224 ± 0.00097 mg/kg for Cd, and 0.00110 ± 0.00084 mg/kg for Cu. Figure 2 presents the observed maximum concentrations of these metals at various sites, with particularly elevated levels at specific locations: B4 for Co (1.01 mg/kg), B8 for Cr (0.725 mg/kg), B6 for Pb (0.211 mg/kg), B4 for Cd (0.0034 mg/kg), and B5 for Cu (0.0024 mg/kg). This study found the relative concentrations of metals in the soil samples to be in the descending order of $Co > Cr > Pb > Cu > Cd$.

The mean concentrations of all five heavy metals were below the permissible limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which are 5.00 mg/kg for Co, 43.4 mg/kg for Cr, 35.8 mg/kg for Pb, 0.99 mg/kg for Cd, and 31.6 mg/kg for Cu (Kawichai et al., 2023). These results indicate that the soil in Dandagoro is not contaminated with these metals at levels that pose a significant environmental or public health risk. The likely reason may be the low background levels of these metals combined with minimal anthropogenic impacts, as indicated in a study on heavy metals in soils from Katsina State (Yaradua et al., 2022). However, the elevated cobalt concentration in B4 location indicates possible localized source of contamination, and underscores the importance of continued monitoring to prevent future accumulation.

Additionally, the mean concentrations of Co (0.225 mg/kg), Cr (0.110 mg/kg), Pb (0.106 mg/kg), Cd (0.00224 mg/kg), and Cu (0.00110 mg/kg) in this study are comparable to values reported by (Samaila et al. 2023) at Dandagoro Quarters, but lower than those reported in irrigation areas by (Sada et al., 2023), where Pb and Cd reached up to 4.01 and 0.022 mg/kg, and also slightly higher than levels at the NYSC camp reported by (Samaila et al. 2022), particularly for Pb (0.028 mg/kg) and Cr (0.554 mg/kg), indicating that Dandagoro soils reflect background levels typical of low-risk, non-industrial areas in Katsina State.

Figure 2: Comparison Chart of Heavy Metal Concentrations in Soil Samples from Dandagoro Settlement.

Assessment of Heavy Metals Pollution

Contamination Factor (CF), Degree of Contamination (DC) and Pollution Load Index (PLI)

Table S5 shows the values of the contamination factor (CF) and pollution load index (PLI) of soil samples collected from Dandagoro settlement. The CF values, arranged in descending order of their mean across all samples, were as follows: Co (0.0563) > Cd (0.0172) > Cr (0.0110) > Pb (0.00623) > Cu (0.0000552). These results indicate that all the CF values are below 1, suggesting a low contamination level for all the studied metals according to the classification by Hakanson (1980), where $CF < 1$ denotes low contamination. The relatively higher mean CF values of Co and Cd, despite being below the threshold, point to a more noticeable anthropogenic contribution compared to other metals.

Figure 3: Comparison chart of Pollution Load index (PLI) and Degree of contamination (DC) of soil samples from Dandagoro settlement.

The PLI values, which provide a composite assessment of the overall level of heavy metal pollution (Adamu et al., 2023), ranged from 0.00136 to 0.00738 across the sampled sites, with a mean value (Mean \pm S.D.) of 0.00351 ± 0.00209 . As shown in Table S5, these PLI values are all significantly less than 1, indicating no considerable pollution in the soils of Dandagoro based on cumulative metal loading.

The spatial trend in PLI and DC values (Figure 3) may reflect metal dispersion attributed to agricultural activities, dumpsites and topography. The decreasing PLI values with distance from suspected anthropogenic sources suggest dilution effects, which aligns with observations in similar environmental studies (Yaradua et al., 2022; Alhassan & Dajal, 2023; Sada et al., 2023).

Geo-Accumulation Index (I_{geo})

Figure 4 illustrates a boxplot of the mean geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) values for heavy metals in the soil samples from the study area. The I_{geo} values range from -8.21 to 1.43 for Co, -5.94 to 2.27 for Cr, -2.82 to 1.25 for Pb, -15.20 to -11.70 for Cd, and -9.55 to -4.97 for Cu. The mean I_{geo} values of Co, Cr, Pb, Cd, and Cu were -1.90 , -2.00 , -0.20 , -12.60 , and -6.70 , respectively (Table S6). According to Müller’s classification, the pollution levels indicate that Co, Cr, Cd, and Cu are in the unpolluted category, while Pb ranges from unpolluted to moderately polluted. The assessment of I_{geo} values suggests minimal anthropogenic influence for most of the metals, with Pb showing the greatest potential for localized contamination.

Figure 4: Boxplot of Geo-accumulation Index (I_{geo}) for Heavy Metals in Soil Samples from the Study Area

Assessment of Health Risk from Heavy Metals

Non-Carcinogenic Risk Assessment

Hazard Quotient (HQ) risk index was used to evaluate the potential health risk related to the non-carcinogenic impacts of metals on soils (Hasaballah et al., 2021). Table 1 presents the results from the HQ risk index values associated with heavy metal exposure in the Dandagoro settlement through ingestion, inhalation, and dermal routes. Among children, cobalt showed the highest HQ values, particularly via dermal contact (5.53×10^{-4}) and ingestion (1.48×10^{-4}), followed by lead through ingestion (3.98×10^{-4}). For adults, cobalt also contributed the most, especially through dermal exposure (2.59×10^{-4}), while other metals such as chromium, cadmium, and copper had minimal impact across all pathways. However, the hazard quotient (HQ) values were all found to be below 1 ($HQ < 1.0$) for both children and adults. This observation suggests that the non-carcinogenic health risk linked to exposure is minimal. The HI values of exposure to heavy metals by individuals in Dandagoro were ranked in descending order as follows: $Co > Pb > Cd > Cr > Cu$ for both children and adults. These results are consistent with the findings of (Kawichai et al., 2023; Yaradua et al., 2022), which indicated that individuals of all age groups showed HQ values below 1.0 when exposed to heavy metals from soil and sediment in agricultural environments. Notably, children showed more sensitivity to this risk than adults, especially through ingestion and dermal pathways.

Table 1: Hazard Quotient (HQ) and Hazard Index (HI) values for non-carcinogenic risk assessment

		INGESTION	INHALATION	DERMAL
HQ for Children	Co	1.48E-04	1.61E-05	5.53E-04
	Cr	9.65E-07	2.36E-06	1.35E-06
	Pb	3.98E-04	1.30E-08	7.36E-06
	Cd	2.95E-05	1.68E-08	8.25E-08
	Cu	3.63E-07	1.05E-11	1.69E-09
	HI	5.77E-04	1.85E-05	5.62E-04
HQ for Adult	Co	1.59E-05	1.18E-05	2.59E-04
	Cr	1.03E-07	1.74E-06	6.33E-07
	Pb	4.26E-05	9.54E-09	3.45E-06
	Cd	3.16E-06	1.24E-08	3.87E-08
	Cu	3.89E-08	7.74E-12	7.94E-10
	HI	6.18E-05	1.36E-05	2.63E-04

Carcinogenic Risk Assessment

Table 2 shows the data on lifetime cancer risk (LCR) that was used to evaluate the long-term effects of exposure to heavy metals. Based on established risk assessment frameworks, it is widely recognized that exposure to toxic heavy metals such as chromium (Cr), lead (Pb), and cadmium (Cd) may be causally linked to the development of cancer in humans (Pavilonis et al., 2017; Kabir et al., 2024). The average LCR values in the soil samples from the Dandagoro settlement were determined for children and adults as follows: Cr ranged from 2.42×10^{-8} to 5.31×10^{-6} , Pb ranged from 8.30×10^{-9} to 1.40×10^{-7} , and Cd ranged from 1.57×10^{-9} to 1.78×10^{-8} in children. For adults, LCR values ranged from 3.51×10^{-9} to 7.71×10^{-7} for Cr, 3.39×10^{-9} to 5.70×10^{-8} for Pb, and 1.94×10^{-10} to 2.20×10^{-9} for Cd. Although some individual values, particularly for Cr in children (5.31×10^{-6} in location B8), slightly exceeded the benchmark level of 1.0×10^{-6} , the mean LCRs for all metals remained within or near the acceptable limits. This suggests a generally low cancer risk from exposure to Cr, Pb, and Cd in the study area.

Moreover, the lifetime cancer incidence rate (cases per one million people) was estimated by multiplying the LCR by 1×10^6 . For children, this equates to approximately 0.81 cases per million for Cr, 0.07 for Pb, and 0.01 for Cd. For adults, the estimated societal risk was 0.12 cases per million for Cr, 0.03 for Pb, and 0.001 for Cd. Children exhibited higher LCR values than adults across all metals and samples, likely due to age-specific factors such as frequent hand-to-mouth behaviors, higher soil ingestion rates, and unique physiological susceptibilities, for instance, children absorb greater proportions of ingested contaminants relative to their body weight, and their exploratory mouthing and pica behaviors raise direct exposure to soil-bound toxins (Carroquino et al., 2012). Consequently, children living near Dandagoro’s agricultural areas or dumpsites may be exposed to carcinogens metals at higher levels compared with other children.

Table 2: Lifetime cancer risk (LCR) values for carcinogenic risk assessment.

Sample Codes	LCR for Children			LCR for Adults		
	Cr	Pb	Cd	Cr	Pb	Cd
B1	3.55E-07	9.76E-08	1.57E-09	5.14E-08	3.98E-08	1.94E-10
B2	3.16E-07	8.93E-08	6.28E-09	4.58E-08	3.64E-08	7.75E-10
B3	5.32E-07	9.28E-08	1.62E-08	7.72E-08	3.78E-08	2.00E-09
B4	8.65E-08	5.82E-08	1.78E-08	1.25E-08	2.37E-08	2.20E-09
B5	2.42E-08	1.13E-07	1.57E-08	3.51E-09	4.63E-08	1.94E-09
B6	3.26E-07	1.40E-07	1.31E-08	4.73E-08	5.70E-08	1.62E-09

B7	7.29E-07	5.47E-08	8.89E-09	1.06E-07	2.23E-08	1.10E-09
B8	5.31E-06	4.02E-08	1.41E-08	7.71E-07	1.64E-08	1.74E-09
B9	4.76E-08	8.97E-09	1.41E-08	6.91E-09	3.66E-09	1.74E-09
B10	3.36E-07	8.30E-09	9.42E-09	4.87E-08	3.39E-09	1.16E-09
Mean	8.07E-07	7.03E-08	1.17E-08	1.17E-07	2.87E-08	1.45E-09
S.D.	1.52E-06	4.15E-08	4.82E-09	2.20E-07	1.69E-08	5.95E-10
Min.	2.42E-08	8.30E-09	1.57E-09	3.51E-09	3.39E-09	1.94E-10
Max	5.31E-06	1.40E-07	1.78E-08	7.71E-07	5.70E-08	2.20E-09

CONCLUSION

This comprehensive study investigated heavy metal concentrations in soils from Dandagoro Settlement, Katsina State, Nigeria, with mean concentrations in a descending order of Co > Cr > Pb > Cu > Cd. Notably, mean concentrations of these elements were within WHO/FAO permissible limits, suggesting minimal contamination. Risk assessment revealed negligible non-carcinogenic risks (HQ < 1) associated with ingestion, inhalation, and dermal exposure pathways. However, the lifetime cancer risk analysis highlighted concerns regarding chromium exposure, particularly in children at specific locations, where the LCR exceeded the acceptable benchmark (>10⁻⁶). Given these findings, we strongly recommend targeted interventions to mitigate potential health threats and ensure the well-being of residents in the study area.

Supplementary Materials: Additional materials can be found at this site: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/11vQWRbh3V0dWLqzncKkyTPvDDTURIUs/view?usp=drivesdk> Table S1: Geographical information of Dandagoro settlement. Table S2: Parameters used to estimate health risk. Table S3: Reference doses (RFD) and cancer slope factors (CSFs) for the contaminants. Table S4: Heavy metals concentration values. Table S5: Contamination factor (CF), Degree of contamination (DC) and Pollution load index (PLI) values. Table S6: Geo-accumulation index (I_{geo}) values.

REFERENCES

- Adamu, S. B., Aliyu, I. F., Musa, L. Y., Kamil, K. K., Afeez, A. O., Muhammad, I. C., Mikailu, A., Rabi, T. A., Garba, I. S., Garba, S. D., Thomas, D. O., & Yakubu, Y. Y. (2023). Quantification of pollution index of selected heavy metals in agricultural soils in Kafin Hausa area, Northwest Nigeria. *UMYU Scientifica*, 2(4), 150–160. <https://doi.org/10.56919/usc.2324.019>
- Afolayan, D. O., Eggleston, C. M., Onwualu, A. P., Adetunji, A. R., Tao, M., & Amankwah, R. K. (2021). Physicochemical Studies for risk identification, assessment, and characterization of artisanal barite mining in Nigeria. *Sustainability*, 13(23), 12982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132312982>
- Aguilera, A. (2021). Health risk of heavy metals in street dust. *Frontiers in Bioscience*, 26(2), 327–345. <https://doi.org/10.2741/4896>
- Alhassan, U. S., & Dajal, J. S. (2023). Health risk assessment from the consumption of moringa oleifera leaves cultivated along River Ginzo, katsina. *FUDMA Journal of Sciences*, 7(6), 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2023-0706-2173>
- Bello, Suleiman & Zakari, Y & Ibeanu, I & Muhammad, B.G.. (2016). Characterization and assessment of heavy metal pollution levels in soils of Dana steel limited dumpsite, Katsina state, Nigeria using geo-accumulation, ecological risk and hazard indices. *Journal of Engineering Research*, 5, 49-61.
- Carroquino, M. J., Posada, M., & Landrigan, P. J. (2012). Environmental toxicology: Children at risk. *Environmental Toxicology*, 239–291. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5764-0_11

- Google Earth Maps. (2025). Satellite image of Dandagoro Settlement (modified). www.googlemaps.com. Retrieved on 8th June, 2025.
- Hakanson, L. (1980). An ecological risk index for aquatic pollution control. a sedimentological approach. *Water Research*, 14(8), 975–1001. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354\(80\)90143-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0043-1354(80)90143-8)
- Hasaballah, A. F., El-Emam, D. A., Ibrahim, M. S., & Hegazy, T. A. (2021). Health risk assessment of heavy metals contamination in sediments of the River Nile, damietta branch using Mathematical Models. *Egyptian Journal of Aquatic Biology and Fisheries*, 25(2), 947–971. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejabf.2021.170342>
- Jaishankar, M., Tseten, T., Anbalagan, N., Mathew, B. B., & Beeregowda, K. N. (2014). Toxicity, mechanism and health effects of some heavy metals. *Interdisciplinary Toxicology*, 7(2), 60–72. <https://doi.org/10.2478/intox-2014-0009>
- Kabir, H. G., Yar'adua, A. I., Matazu, K. I., Lawal, R. G., Kabir, Z. G., Bala, M. G., Mukhtar, M. U., Sani, A. S., Bashir, A., & Matazu, H. K. (2024). Heavy metal contamination risks in environmental and vegetable samples around a metal workshop in Kofar MARUSA, Katsina Metropolis. *UMYU Journal of Microbiology Research (UJMR)*, 440–451. <https://doi.org/10.47430/ujmr.2493.052>
- Kawichai, S., Prapamontol, T., Santijitpakdee, T., & Bootdee, S. (2023). Risk assessment of heavy metals in sediment samples from the mae chaem river, Chiang Mai, Thailand. *Toxics*, 11(9), 780. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxics11090780>
- Olagunju, T., Olagunju, A., Akawu, I., & Ugokwe, C. (2020). Quantification and risk assessment of heavy metals in groundwater and soil of residential areas around awotan landfill, Ibadan, Southwest-Nigeria. *Journal of Toxicology and Risk Assessment*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.23937/2572-4061.1510033>
- Oni, A. A., Babalola, S. O., Adeleye, A. D., Olagunju, T. E., Amama, I. A., Omole, E. O., Adegboye, E. A., & Ohore, O. G. (2022). Non-carcinogenic and carcinogenic health risks associated with heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in well-water samples from an automobile junk market in Ibadan, SW-Nigeria. *Heliyon*, 8(9). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e10688>
- Paint Maps. (2025). Sample maps of Batagarawa generated with map cropping (masking) tool. paintmaps.com. Retrieved on 8th June, 2025.
- Pavilonis, B., Grassman, J., Johnson, G., Diaz, Y., & Caravanos, J. (2017). Characterization and risk of exposure to elements from artisanal gold mining operations in the Bolivian Andes. *Environmental Research*, 154, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2016.12.010>
- Samaila, A., Aniefiok, F. A., & Joseph, E. (2025). Exploration of concentration and variation of heavy metals in some borehole water from basement formation in Charanchi Local Government, Katsina State of Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 25(3), 090–102. <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.3.0611>
- Samaila, A., Bello, S., Iliyasu, S. R., & Sani, M. (2022). The background concentration of some heavy metals at NYSC Orientation Camp Layout, Katsina. *FUDMA Journal of Sciences*, 6(4), 150–155. <https://doi.org/10.33003/fjs-2022-0604-1051>
- Samaila, A., Bello, S., Salele, S., & Iliyasu, S. R. (2023). Analysis of some heavy metal background concentration at Dandagoro Quarters, Katsina, Katsina State, Nigeria. *UMYU Scientifica*, 2(1), 133–139. <https://doi.org/10.56919/usci.2123.016>
- Shuvo, S. D., Mallick, T., Khanum, L., Chakraborty, T. K., Hossain, Md. S., Parvin, R., Roy, D., & Elahi, Md. T. (2025). Carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic health risk assessment of heavy metals and trace elements of poultry and domestic chicken tissues marketed in Bangladesh. *Applied Food Research*, 5(1), 101025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2025.101025>
- Uba, G., Abdulhadi, Y., Lawan, M. A., Ahmad, A., & Kabir, A. (2022). Health risk assessment of heavy metals from selected fruits and vegetables sold in Dutse ultra-modern market, Jigawa State.

Journal of Biochemistry, Microbiology and Biotechnology, 10(2), 52–55.
<https://doi.org/10.54987/jobimb.v10i2.758>

- Yaradua, A. I., Bungudu, J. I., Shuaibu, L., Nasir, A., Usman, A., Kankia, I. H., Matazu, N. U., Suleiman, Z. A., Sada, A. A., Rumah, F. A., Bello, U., Tukur, A. B., Sani, A. S., Lawal, R. G., Matazu, H. K., Sani, A. K., Kabir, Z. G., Yaradua, A. I., Kabir, H. G., ... Muhammad, A. N. (2023). Health risk assessment of heavy metals in vegetable: The contribution of illegal mining and armed banditry to heavy metal pollution in Katsina State, Nigeria. *Journal of Scientific Research and Reports*, 29(5), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jsrr/2023/v29i51744>
- Yaradua, A. I., Shuaibu, L., Alhassan, A. J., Bungudu, J. I., Usman, A., Nasir, A., & Yaradua, I. A. (2022). Health risk assessment of some selected heavy metals in agricultural soils from Katsina State, North-Western Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Applied Chemistry Research*, 47–58. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajacr/2022/v11i4209>